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RESEARCH PAPER

AMELIORATIVE EFFECTS OF VITAMIN C ON METHAMPHETAMINE-INDUCED OXIDATIVE STRESS AND NEUROBEHAVIORAL CHANGES IN RATS

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ABSTRACT

This 21-day study determined the ameliorative effects of vitamin C on methamphetamine-induced (Meth-induced) oxidative stress and neurobehavioral changes in adolescent male Wistar rats. A total of 35 rats were randomly divided into 7 groups of 5 rats each (Groups A – G). Groups A (control) received normal rat feed and water, while groups B and C received 5 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg body weight of Meth, respectively. Group D and E received 300 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C, respectively. Group F received 5 mg/kg body weight of Meth + 300 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C, and G received 10 mg/kg body weight of Meth + 600 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C. Twenty-four hours after the last administration and neurobehavioral tests, the rats were anesthetized under chloroform vapor and sacrificed for the collection of tissue and blood sample for biochemical analysis. Oxidative stress markers and enzyme activities were evaluated using standard commercial kits. The results showed statistically significant reduction in body weight, which was ameliorated by vitamin C administration. Improvements in cognitive function and oxidative stress parameters were also observed in the co-treatment groups, underscoring the antioxidant and hepato-protective potentials of vitamin C against Meth-induced toxicity.

Key words: Neuroprotection, Vitamine C, Methamphetamine, Neurobehaviors

INTRODUCTION

Methamphetamine (METH), a potent central nervous system (CNS) stimulant, is widely abused for its euphoric effects, which occur through the rapid release of dopamine and norepinephrine in the brain (Prakash *et al.*, 2017; Liu and Si

2024). Initially synthesized in 1887 at the University of Berlin, methamphetamine was used by soldiers during World War II to suppress appetite and enhance alertness (Edinoff *et al.*, 2022). However, its recreational use has led to significant health problems, including cardiopulmonary symptoms like chest pain, palpitations, and shortness of breath, as well as CNS effects such as anxiety, agitation, delusions, and seizures (Edinoff, 2022; Lawson, 2022). Chronic use can lead to psychosis, strokes, and long-term neurodegenerative damage, particularly in the prefrontal cortex (NIDA, 2022; Kaufman, 2022). Neuroimaging studies have shown that methamphetamine abuse leads to structural and metabolic changes in the brain, especially in the cortical regions (Hart *et al.*, 2012).

The impact of methamphetamine abuse extends beyond the brain as it affects various physiological systems (Jan *et al.*, 2012). One of the prominent effects is its influence on body weight as chronic methamphetamine usage is associated with severe weight loss due to its appetite-suppressant properties (Yasaei and Saadabadi, 2023). Additionally, methamphetamine induces significant oxidative stress, which damages cells and tissues throughout the body (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). This oxidative damage contributes to the neurotoxic effects observed in long-term methamphetamine users, impairing cognitive function and increasing the risk of neurodegenerative diseases (Kaufman, 2022; Lawson, 2022).

With approximately 24 million people using methamphetamine worldwide, the drug's widespread misuse presents a growing public health challenge (Edinoff *et al.*, 2022). The high potential for addiction is compounded by the drug's easy production and affordability (Carter and Davis, 2023). Despite its harmful effects, treatment for methamphetamine addiction remains limited, and the prevalence of methamphetamine use continues to rise, particularly in rural areas (Cornett, 2022).

In this context, there is increasing interest in potential interventions to mitigate the damage caused by methamphetamine abuse. One such candidate is Vitamin C, an essential nutrient and potent antioxidant known for its neuroprotective properties. Vitamin C is vital for the synthesis of neurotransmitters, collagen, and L-carnitine, and has shown promise in protecting the brain from oxidative damage (Carr and Frei, 1999; Jacob, 2002). Given its antioxidant effects and ability to support immune function, Vitamin C may offer a protective mechanism against methamphetamine-induced neurotoxicity.

Impaired cognitive and emotional regulation, leading to the behavioral changes due to brain damage has been recognized in methamphetamine ingestion (Jones and Graff-Radford, 2021). Thus, investigating the neuroprotective effects of vitamin C against methamphetamine-induced toxicity is a critical step in addressing the long-term consequences of methamphetamine addiction. This study is therefore designed to determine the ameliorative effects of vitamin C on methamphetamine-induced (Meth-induced) oxidative stress and neurobehavioral changes in adolescent male Wistar rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Duration of the Study: This study was carried out at the animal house of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi campus, Anambra State, Nigeria, and it lasted for 21 days.

Collection of Experimental Substances: The drug methamphetamine was obtained from the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency, in Anambra State, Nigeria, while vitamin C was obtained from Madobi Pharmaceutical Stores at Nnewi, Anambra State. These substances were weighed for appropriate administration using an electronic weighing balance (an ATOM A-120 scale made in China).

Experimental Animals: Thirty-five (35) young male Wistar rats were procured from Research Enterprise farms at the University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Perspex cages fitted with wire gauze tops for ventilation, were used to house the experimental rats divided into seven groups of five rats each a control (group A) and six test groups (B, C, D, E, F and G). During the period of acclimatization, the rats were fed *ad libitum* with water and guinea feed pellets from Agro Feed Mill Nigeria Ltd.

Ethical Considerations: All the animals were treated following the approval of the ethical committee with the number FBMS/EA/1220, College of Health Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus, in line with the “Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals” (NRC 2011). Additionally, the researchers balanced the scientific requirements with ethical considerations to minimize the number of animals used, while also ensuring meaningful results.

Experimental Design and Protocols: The animals were allowed to acclimatize for a period of two weeks at the animal house of the Department of Anatomy, College of Health Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Nnewi Campus, Nigeria, before their baseline weights were taken, under a controlled room temperature of about 25-28°C, relative humidity of about 60-80%, and photo-periodicity of 12h day/12h night. They were fed ad libitum with water and guinea feed pellets from Agro Feed Mill Nigeria Ltd. The test groups were subjected to varied treatment with meth and vitamin C, as well as neurobiological tests.

Drug Treatment: Methamphetamine and vitamin C solution was administered to the experimental animals using a calibrated 2ml syringe and an oral cannula. Group A (control), received normal rat feed and water only, while groups B and C received 5 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg body weight of Meth, respectively. Groups D and E received 300 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C, respectively. Group F received 5 mg/kg body weight of Meth +300 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C, and G received 10 mg/kg body weight of Meth +600 mg/kg body weight of vitamin C. Twenty-four hours after the last administration and neurobehavioral tests, the rats were anesthetized under chloroform vapor and dissected for tissue and blood sample collection for laboratory analysis. Marker enzymes evaluations were performed using the random kit method.

Behavioral Function Test: This assessment was based on the natural reliance of rats on environmental cues for essential behaviors such as locating food, recognizing social and mating partners, and avoiding predators, all of which depend on intact motor function (Zou *et al.*, 2015). Accurate evaluation of motor abilities in rats exposed to inhaled toxic substances is therefore critical for understanding basal ganglia-related behaviors (Zou *et al.*, 2015). In this study, the Morris water maze test, widely regarded as the "gold standard" in behavioral neuroscience (Nunez, 2008), was employed. A 36-liter basin was filled with water maintained at approximately 26°C, and an escape platform was placed at the center, extending one inch above the surface during pre-training to signal its presence. Each rat was gently placed at the edge of the basin and released into clear water while a video camera recorded the session; the time taken to locate and mount the platform was recorded. Afterward, the rat was removed, dried, and allowed a one-hour recovery period. For the actual test, the platform was removed, and milk was added to make the water opaque. Each rat was then reintroduced into the water, and the time taken by the rat to cross the midpoint of the basin, where the platform had previously been located, was measured as an indicator of spatial memory and motor coordination.

Termination of treatment: The administration lasted for a period of 21 days. At the end of the 21st day, administration was terminated. The behavioral changes were tested across the four groups of animals to identify the animals that have lost their motor function. Twenty-four hours after the last exposure, following the behavioral test, the animals were weighed, and then anesthetized under chloroform vapor for tissue and blood sample collection.

Biochemical Analysis: The brain tissues were taken to the Biochemistry Department for the analysis of Malondialdehyde (MDA)/specific antioxidant capacities.

Homogenization: One gram of the respective organs were weighed and put into 10ml of 0.9% normal saline each and homogenized with homogenizer at room temperature. After this, each of the samples was centrifuged at 3000rpm for 20min at room temperature. The supernatant was separated and stored in a refrigerator at 2 degrees Celsius for further analysis.

Lipid Peroxidation: Lipid peroxidation (LPO) was investigated using the method described by Ohkawa *et al.*, 1979. One milliliter (1mL) of 10% chilled (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added to One milliliter (1mL) of 10% homogenate, incubated at 37°C for 10 min and centrifuged at 2,500 rpm for 15 min at room temperature. One milliliter (1mL) of 0.67% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) was added to 1 ml of supernatant and kept in a boiling water bath for 10-15 min. After cooling, 1 ml of distilled water was added to it and absorbance will be taken at 530 nm. The results will be expressed as nmol MDA/h/g tissue.

Nonenzymatic antioxidant: Glutathione (GSH) was investigated with the method described by Ellman (1959). One milliliter of 5% TCA (w/v) was added to 1 ml of 10% homogenate. The suspension was left for 30 min and centrifuged at 2,500 rpm for 15 min. 0.5 ml of supernatant was taken and 2.5 ml of 5'5'-dithionitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) added. The suspension was then shaken thoroughly and read at 412 nm and the results expressed as $\mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue.

Enzymatic antioxidants: Superoxide dismutase (SOD) was investigated with the method described by Kakkar *et al.* (1984). A total of 650 μl of sodium pyrophosphate buffer was added to 50 μl of brain supernatant fraction; 50 μl phenazinemethosulfate (PMS), 150 μl of nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT), and 100 μl nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) was added and the mixture vortexed thoroughly. The reaction mixture was incubated for 90s and 500 μl glacial acetic acid was added to stop the reaction. Two milliliter of n-butanol was added, and vortexed thoroughly. This was kept at room temperature for 10 min. Absorbance was measured at 560 nm and the results were expressed as $\mu\text{mol/min/mg}$ protein.

Data Analysis: Data was analyzed using SPSS version 27.0.1 software package. Mean and standard deviation were obtained and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare values between groups. Data was expressed as Mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) and then considered statistically significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULT

Body Weight Changes

The results shown in tables 1 reveal statistically significant alterations in body weight across all treatment groups.

Table 1: Effect of Methamphetamine and Vitamin C on body weights of rats in all the groups.

Groups	Weight (g)	Mean \pm SEM	p-value
Group A	Initial	210.05 \pm 0.8	0.044
	Final	235.33 \pm 1.76	
Group B	Initial	202.33 \pm 0.88	0.001
	Final	196.67 \pm 1.20	
Group C	Initial	201.33 \pm 0.88	0.001
	Final	192.00 \pm 2.00	
Group D	Initial	200.33 \pm 0.88	0.001
	Final	209.00 \pm 2.00	
Group E	Initial	203.02 \pm 0.13	0.001
	Final	211.05 \pm 0.56	
Group F	Initial	200.33 \pm 0.67	0.001
	Final	195.67 \pm 0.88	
Group G	Initial	201.33 \pm 0.88	0.001
	Final	194.67 \pm 1.20	

Data was analyzed using Student dependent T-test and values were considered significant at $P < 0.05$,
 **=Significance when compared to the control group.

The control group (A) showed a significant increase from 210.05 ± 0.8 to 235.33 ± 1.76 ($P < 0.05$), while groups B and C, administered low and high doses of methamphetamine respectively, experienced significant weight reductions from 202.33 ± 0.88 to 196.67 ± 1.20 , and from 201.33 ± 0.88 to 192.00 ± 2.00 ($P < 0.05$), respectively. In contrast, groups D and E, which received vitamin C alone, exhibited moderate weight gains, increasing from 200.33 ± 0.88 to 209.00 ± 2.00 and from 203.02 ± 0.13 to 211.05 ± 0.56 , respectively. However, in Groups F and G, which received combined methamphetamine and vitamin C treatment, body weight still declined significantly—from 200.33 ± 0.67 to 195.67 ± 0.88 and from 201.33 ± 0.88 to 194.67 ± 1.20 , respectively—indicating that although vitamin C conferred some protective effects, it did not fully reverse methamphetamine-induced weight loss. These outcomes confirm a statistically significant impact of methamphetamine on body weight, with only partial mitigation by vitamin C, thus rejecting the null hypothesis

Neurobehavioral Function Test:

The Morris Water Maze test results shown in table 2 below, demonstrates significant differences in escape latency among the treatment groups ($p < 0.05$). Rats in the methamphetamine-treated groups (B and C) exhibited significantly prolonged escape latency times, suggesting impaired spatial learning and memory. In contrast, groups treated with vitamin C alone (D and E) showed significantly improved performance compared to the methamphetamine-only groups, as reflected by reduced escape latency. However, the combined treatment group F showed no statistically significant improvement, while group G, despite receiving both methamphetamine and vitamin C, still exhibited significantly increased escape latency similar to group B. These findings imply that methamphetamine impairs cognitive performance, while vitamin C demonstrates a potential neuroprotective effect, particularly when administered independently.

Table 2: Result of Morris Water Maze Test Conducted on Meth and Vitamin C induced rats.

	Groups	Mean \pm SEM	p-value	f-value
Morris Water Maze Test- Escape latency (Seconds)	Group A	16.52 ± 2.93		6.369
	Group B	40.25 ± 3.84	0.044	
	Group C	43.50 ± 11.23	0.002	
	Group D	22.50 ± 5.23	0.001	
	Group E	24.35 ± 9.59	0.001	
	Group F	27.20 ± 4.54	0.341	
	Group G	40.25 ± 3.84	0.044	

Data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA, and values were considered significant at $P < 0.05$. *Significance when compared to the control group.

Biochemical Analysis:

Table 3 below presents the results of the biochemical analysis, which revealed statistically significant alterations ($p < 0.05$) in oxidative stress markers across treatment groups. Methamphetamine administration (Groups B and C) led to elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels and reduced glutathione (GSH) and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activities, indicating increased oxidative stress. Vitamin C treatment alone (Groups D and E) significantly improved antioxidant markers compared to the methamphetamine-only groups. Although combined treatment with vitamin C (Groups F and G) partially restored antioxidant levels, values remained significantly different from the control in most cases. These results suggest that vitamin C confers protective antioxidant effects against methamphetamine-induced oxidative damage, but the mitigation is dose-and context-dependent

Table 2: Oxidative Stress Biomarkers

Parameter	Groups	Mean ± SEM	<i>p</i> -value	<i>F</i> -value
MDA	Group A	3.42 ± 0.01	–	–
	Group B	3.64 ± 0.02*	0.000	44.160
	Group C	3.72 ± 0.06*	0.000	–
	Group D	3.28 ± 0.06*	0.000	–
	Group E	3.24 ± 0.06*	0.000	–
	Group F	3.52 ± 0.01*	0.000	–
	Group G	3.64 ± 0.02*	0.000	–
GSH	Group A	1.44 ± 0.02	–	–
	Group B	1.30 ± 0.03*	0.031	14.246
	Group C	1.25 ± 0.02*	0.002	–
	Group D	1.25 ± 0.02*	0.002	–
	Group E	1.25 ± 0.02*	0.002	–
	Group F	1.40 ± 0.01	0.890	–
	Group G	3.64 ± 0.02*	0.031	–
SOD	Group A	8.56 ± 0.02	–	–
	Group B	7.54 ± 0.01*	0.000	1336.758
	Group C	7.33 ± 0.03*	0.000	–
	Group D	7.33 ± 0.03*	0.000	–
	Group E	7.33 ± 0.03*	0.000	–
	Group F	7.80 ± 0.02*	0.000	–
	Group G	7.54 ± 0.01*	0.000	–

Keys: MDA = Malondialdehyde; SOD = superoxide dismutase; GSH = glutathione; *: Indicates statistically significant difference compared to the control group (*p* < 0.05).

DISCUSSION

This study revealed significant alterations in body weight across the experimental groups. The control group showed a slight increase in body weight, consistent with expected physiological conditions. In contrast, groups B and C, which received methamphetamine without vitamin C supplementation, experienced significant weight loss, highlighting the deleterious impact of methamphetamine on overall health. These results are consistent with findings by Nnabuihe *et al.* (2025) and Miller *et al.* (2021).

Group D, which received vitamin C following methamphetamine exposure, demonstrated improvement in body weight gain, suggesting a mitigating effect of vitamin C on methamphetamine-induced physiological damage. Meanwhile, Group E, treated with vitamin C alone, did not show significant weight changes—possibly due to the dosage or duration of treatment, as supported by Carr and Lykkesfeldt (2023).

The Morris Water Maze test further provided insight into cognitive function. The control group (A) exhibited an average escape latency of 16.52 ± 2.93 seconds, reflecting normal spatial learning and memory. Groups B and C, both exposed to methamphetamine, showed prolonged escape latencies (27.20 ± 4.54 and 40.25 ± 3.84 seconds, respectively), indicating impaired cognitive function. Although Group C received vitamin C, its increased latency suggests a dose-dependent but limited reversal of methamphetamine-induced cognitive deficits (Kocot *et al.*, 2017).

Groups D and E, despite vitamin C treatment, also displayed elevated latencies (43.50 ± 11.23 seconds), reinforcing the notion that vitamin C alone may not fully restore cognitive performance. These outcomes are in agreement with Nnabuihe *et al.* (2025), pointing to the need for optimized dosing or additional interventions.

Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) in Groups C, D, and E suggests partial neuroprotection from vitamin C. However, the lack of full cognitive recovery supports the view that vitamin C's neuroprotective effects are limited and may require adjusted dosage and duration (Kocot *et al.*, 2017). These findings echo existing literature indicating that while antioxidants like vitamin C may reduce methamphetamine-induced neurotoxicity, they may not completely restore function.

Biochemical analyses supported these findings. Although vitamin C-treated groups showed reductions in MDA and modulations in GSH and SOD levels, these did not fully normalize, suggesting incomplete restoration of antioxidant balance. This may be due to the complex nature of methamphetamine-induced oxidative stress, which likely requires multi-targeted or extended therapeutic strategies (Asuku *et al.*, 2024).

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that methamphetamine induces biochemical and functional disruptions. Vitamin C, due to its antioxidant properties, exhibited a protective effect by attenuating methamphetamine-induced toxicity. Therefore, vitamin C may have potential clinical application in managing methamphetamine withdrawal and aiding in the restoration of physiological and cognitive function.

Recommendation

Since this study focused on biochemical and neurobehavioral changes, future research should assess the impact on key neurotransmitters and inflammatory markers, particularly at the molecular level, as well as the cytoarchitecture of the associated regions of the brain. Additionally, extending the study to female rats may provide insight into potential sex-based differences in methamphetamine toxicity and antioxidant response.

Limitation of the Study

This study was limited to anthropometric measurements, neurobehavioral tests, and biochemical assays. Molecular markers, including inflammatory and apoptotic pathways, were not assessed. Practical constraints such time, budget, and animal availability also influenced sample size and study design.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

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Abugu JI coordinated the drafting of the manuscript including submission for peer review, revisions and perusal of the Galley Proof.

